

A ligand free protocol using $\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2$ @Mont K-10 as versatile reusable catalyst for efficient homocoupling of arylboronic acids for synthesis of symmetric biaryls

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Biaryls are an important class of organic compounds that occur in many natural products and they have a wide variety of applications in drugs, agrochemicals, dyes, semi-conductors, and asymmetric syntheses. A versatile, eco-friendly, recyclable, heterogeneous catalyst has been developed for the efficient synthesis of symmetric biaryls from aryl boronic acids. The developed protocol for homocoupling of aryl boronic acid to symmetric biaryls is based on copper acetate supported on acid activated Mont K-10 which is ligand free, mild, inexpensive and compatible with wide range of functional groups and exhibit excellent yields. The catalyst is characterised by FTIR, ESR, XRD, SEM-EDX, BET surface area measurement and the catalyst can be separated from the reaction mixture by simple centrifugation and reused upto five cycles without significant loss in activity

Keywords: Copper, Mont K-10, homocoupling, arylboronic acid and biaryl.

Introduction

Biaryl formation is considered to be one of the most important processes from both synthetic and industrial point of view. Both symmetrical and unsymmetrical products have got versatile application in the field of drugs, dyes, agrochemicals, semiconductors, polymers as well as in optically active ligands¹⁻³. The synthetic uses of arylboronic acids are more common as they are more stable and less toxic than other organometallic reagents. Recently, there is increase in the interest in aryl boronic acids among chemists because of its easy availability, stability and non-toxic nature⁴⁻⁷. Development of environment friendly methodology for homocoupling of aryl boronic acid is another challenging task because usual protocols have major limitations such as (1) expensive metals such as Pd⁸⁻¹⁰, Au^{11,12}, Rh¹³ etc. are used, (2) lack of reusability, (3) additional ligands are used extensively, (4) longer reaction time and (5) need of high temperatures to complete the reaction. As part of our ongoing research to develop eco-friendly, easily available and cost effective heterogeneous catalyst for an efficient synthesis of biaryls from homocoupling of aryl boronic acids, we have prepared $\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2$ impregnated Mont K-10 to see its efficacy in synthesis of symmetric biaryls. Generally clays have a wide applications namely in the field of industry, agriculture, phar-

maceuticals, surface coating and ceramics because of its easy availability, inexpensiveness and environmentally safe disposal¹⁴⁻¹⁸. Moreover, clay is highly acclaimed in the field of catalysis both as a catalyst and catalyst support due to its non-corrosive properties, strong acidity, mild reaction condition, high yield, easy handling and easy separation^{19,20}. On acidification, the OH group of the clay was replaced by H⁺, which also removed the scope of H-bonding, thereby increasing surface area, pore volume, pore diameter and higher surface acidity. The different oxidation states of copper namely Cu⁰, Cu^I, Cu^{II} associate well with a large number of different functional groups via Lewis acid interactions or π -coordination which catalyze Cu for oxidation and oxidative union of many substrates. Dar and coworkers¹⁹ have prepared $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_x$ encapsulated over Mont-KSF for selective oxidation of aryl boronic acid to biaryls without base. Kirai *et al.*²⁰ reported that the homocoupling of arylboronic acids carried out in isopropanol in the presence of $\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2$ using 1,10-phenanthroline as a ligand. In continuation of our study of clay supported heterogeneous transition metal catalysts in various organic synthesis and transformations²¹⁻²⁴ we report here Mont K-10 supported $\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2$ as a heterogeneous catalyst system for homocoupling of arylboronic acids at room temperature without using any ligands or co-catalyst at room

Fig. 2. XRD pattern of (i) Mont K-10 (ii) Cu(OAc)₂@Mont K-10 (left).

Fig 3: ESR spectrum of Cu(OAc)₂@Mont K-10 (right).

3630.03 cm⁻¹, 3635.82 cm⁻¹, 3631 cm⁻¹ for clay, activated clay and Cu^{II}@clay correspond to O-H stretching vibration. However the intensity decreases on immobilization of Cu in the clay. In powder XRD^{19,22} the peaks for Mont K-10 [Fig. 2(i)] appears at 2θ = 8.7°, 17.5°, 19.25°, 34.74°, 62.06° and also show characteristic peaks for Cu^{II} acetate at 39.77°, 42.61°, 50.28° which confirms the presence of copper in the catalyst which is shown in the [Fig. 2(ii)]. The ESR spectrum of the catalyst (Fig. 3) recorded at liquid nitrogen temperature in magnetically dilute form for Cu^{II} species. The *g* value as shown in Fig. 3 is found to be 2.12 which indicate the copper has paramagnetic centres and it is in +2 oxidation state. The specific surface area measurement of the copper acetate supported on acid activated Mont K-10 reveals that the value decreases to 42.663 m² g⁻¹ from 59.590 m² g⁻¹, which indicates the impregnation of the copper inside the pores on the clay matrix, resulting in decrease of surface area. From ICP-AES and SEM-EDX analysis, we are able to determine the metal attachment on the surface of the clay. The amount of metal content in the cupric acetate@Mont K-10 catalyst is found to be 0.26 mol% per 60 mg of the catalyst. From the SEM-EDX analysis it was confirmed that Cu is present in the catalyst [Fig. 4(d)]. Initially, we have chosen phenylboronic acid as a starting material to carry out the optimization studies. The reaction was studied with various solvents, bases and catalyst loading on homocoupling reactions. Various solvents such as DMSO, DMF, toluene, methanol, dichloromethane, water were optimised to perform the reaction. Out of these DMF facilitated the reaction with excellent yields. However, very less amount of product was

formed in the absence of a base. All reactions were carried out at room temperature under aerobic condition. The reaction was performed with different bases including KOH, K₂CO₃, Na₂CO₃ in DMF solvent at room temperature and yield of the biphenyl was found to increase in case of KOH base. The excellent results of the catalyst made us further optimize the catalyst loading. An excellent yield of the desired product was obtained in the presence of 60 mg of the catalyst using 1 mmol of phenylboronic acid. However, no progress in the yield was observed by further increasing to 100 mg catalyst loading. Moreover, yield of product from the coupling reaction was low when the concentration of the cata-

Table 1. Optimization of reaction conditions for biaryl synthesis from phenylboronic acid

Entry	Solvent	Catalyst (mg)	Yield (%)
1	H ₂ O	50	–
2	CH ₃ OH	55	–
3	C ₂ H ₅ OH	60	–
4	CH ₃ CN	60	–
5	CH ₂ Cl ₂	60	trace
6	Toluene	60	trace
7	DMSO	60	20
8	DMF	60	80
9	DMF	50	70
10	DMF	70	80
11	DMF	–	–

^aReaction conditions: Phenylboronic acid (1 mmol), catalyst (50–70 mg), solvent (5 ml) time 4 h. ^bIsolated yield. For 60 mg catalyst the amount of Cu is 0.26 mol%.

Fig. 4. (a) SEM image of Mont K-10, (b) EDX of Mont K-10, (c) SEM image of $\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2@$ Mont K-10 and (d) EDX of $\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2@$ Mont K-10.

lyst was decreased from 60 to 10 mg. Moreover without catalyst reaction does not proceed. The performance of $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}@$ Mont K-10 catalyst at optimized reaction conditions helps us to determine general compatibility of the catalyst with wide range of substituted arylboronic acids. The homocoupling reactions of various arylboronic acids have been examined and results are shown in Table 2. The homocoupling of different *para*-substituted arylboronic acids such as $-\text{CH}_3$, $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{C}$ -, $-\text{Cl}$, $(\text{CF}_3)_3\text{C}$ - gave corresponding biaryls in good to excellent yields whereas aryl boronic acids bearing $-\text{Cl}$, $-\text{CH}_3$, group at *meta* position provided excellent yields of corresponding biaryls. Remarkably, heterocyclic boronic acids such as 2-thienylboronic acid and benzofuran-2-boronic acid has undergone homocoupling reaction and provided excellent yield.

Reusability of the catalyst:

There is a great demand for green chemical protocols therefore reusability and easy recovery of the catalyst is an important ways to achieve sustainable and economically viable processes. For reusability process 2-thienyl boronic acid has been chosen for the homocoupling reaction. The catalyst was recovered by simple filtration and washed 2–3 times with distilled water followed by acetone and finally dried in

Fig. 5. Reusability of the catalyst.

an air oven and reused for next cycle. In this way the process is repeated for other four consecutive cycles. To investigate catalyst leaching we have carried out ICP-AES analysis of the filtrate after 5th catalytic cycle. The catalyst clearly indicates that there was negligible loss or leaching of copper species (0.47 ppm) during the course of the reaction and suggesting that copper was held tightly to the clay facilitating the recycling of the catalyst.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we report a cost effective, mild and heterogeneous catalyst for efficient synthesis of symmetric biaryls from aryl boronic acids. The catalyst is easily recoverable and reused for another four cycles without significant loss in its activity.

Table 2. Copper catalysed homocoupling reactions of arylboronic acids

Entry	Substrate	Product	Time (h)	Yield ^b (%)
1		5	85	
2		5	90	
3		3	94	
4		4	90	
5		4	90	
6		5	87	
7		5	95	
8		5	90	
9		4	89	
10		5	90	

^aReaction conditions: Arylboronic acid (1 mmol), catalyst (60 mg, 0.26 mol% Cu), DMF (5 ml), KOH (1mmol). ^bIsolated yield.

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